

TASAVVUF TARIQATIGA OID NAZARIYALAR EVOLYUTSIYASI.

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Annotatsiya. Zamoni saodatda va undan keying dastlabki vaqtlarda aqoid, fiqh va boshqa islomiy ilmlar qatori tasavvuf ham alohida ajrab chiqqan emasdi. O'sha davrdagi musulmonlar Rasululoh sallohu alayhi vassalamning hayotlik chog'larida barcha narsada u zotning o'zlariga ergashar edilar.

Kalit so'zlar: tasavvuf, sufiylik g'oyalar, fikr, so'z.

EVOLUTION OF THEORIES REGARDING THE SECT OF MYSTICISM.

Abstract. In modern Bliss and beyond, mysticism, among other Islamic Sciences, was not isolated in the early days. The Muslims of that time followed him in all things in the life of rasululah Sallahu alayhi vassalam.

Key words: mysticism, Sufism ideas, thought, word.

ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ ТЕОРИЙ МИСТИЧЕСКОГО УЧЕНИЯ.

Аннотация. Суфизм, как и другие исламские науки, не выделялся в отдельность в эпоху Садата и в раннее время после него. Мусульмане того времени во все времена жизни Посланника Аллаха (да благословит его Аллах и приветствует) вассалов во всем следовали за самим имамом.

Ключевые слова: мистика, суфизм идеи, мысль, слово.

Tasavvuf tariqatlari insonlarni ruxan poklanishga, halolikka, haqiqat yo'lidan yurishga, undovchi insoniy, axloqiy tamoillarni shakllantruvchi yo'ldir. Tarixdan bizga ma'lumki ushbu yo'l asosida yashagan, insonlarni to'g'ri yashashga chorlagan, insonlar hayotini faoliyatini yengillashtirgan, ularga naf keltirgan ne-ne buyuk siymolarimiz mavjud. Ularning hayot faoliyati biz uchun ibrat maktabi vazifasini o'taydi. Bunday buyuk ajdodlarimizga misol qilib buyuk sarkarda, Temuriylar davlati asoschisi Amir Temur xazratlarini, o'z davrida valiy darajasida ulug'langan xazrat Xoja Ubaydullox Axrorini, g'azal mulkinging sultoni Mir Alisher Navoiy xazratlarini keltirishimiz mumkin. Tasavvuf tariqatlari tarixiga nazar soladigan bo'lsak undagi g'oyalar, ta'limotlar necha asrlar davomida axloq singari zamon o'zgargani singari u xam sayqallanib, takomillashib borgan. Quyida ushbu tarixiy jarayonga qisqacha to'xtalib o'tamiz.

Zamoni saodatda va undan keying dastlabki vaqtlarda aqoid, fiqh va boshqa islomiy ilmlar qatori tasavvuf ham alohida ajrab chiqqan emasdi. O'sha davrdagi musulmonlar Rasululoh sallohu alayhi vassalamning hayotlik chog'larida barcha narsada u zotning o'zlariga ergashar edilar.

Keyinchalik esa sahobalar o'zlari Qur'on va sunnatdan kerakli xulosalarni olib, amal qilib yurdilar. O'sha paytda ruhiy kamolotga, zikr va zohidlikka moyil zotlar turli oyat va va hadislarni o'zlari uchun dalil topib, mazkur ishlarni o'z hayotlariga tatbiq qildilar.

Bu borada sahobai kiromlar ichida to'rt roshid xalifa Abu Zar G'ifforiy, Abdulloh ibn Amr, Abu Dardo, Abdulloh ibn Abbos, Abdulloh ibn Umar, Salmon Forsiy, as'hobi suffa roziollohu anhum va boshqalar ko'zga ko'ringan edilar.

Tobeinlar avlodi esa boshqa barcha ilmlar qatori, ruhiy tarbiya va nafsni jilovlash ilmini ham sahobalardan qabul qilib oldilar.

Ular orasidan tasavvuf yoʻnalishini belgilashda va uning ilm sifatida shakllanishiga oʻzlarining kata hissalarini qoʻshgan zotlaryetishib chiqadilar. Bulardan Uvays Karaniy, Hasan Basriy, Said Ibn Musayyab, Jafar Sodiq va boshqalarni barcha eʼtirof etib, zikr qiladilar.

Tasavvuf, sufiylik — islomda insonni ruhiy va axloqiy jihatdan komillik sari yoʻllovchi taʼlimot. Tasavvuf soʻzining oʻzagi va mazmuni haqida olimlar turli fikr va taxminlar bildirishgan. Ular ichida Ibn Xaldunning fikri haqiqatga yaqin deb eʼtirof etilgan. U "Muqaddima" asarida tasavvuf "suvf" — "jun", "poʻstin" soʻzidan olingan boʻlishi kerak, zero qadimdan tarkidunyo qilgan zohidlar jundan toʻqilgan kiyim yoki poʻstin kiyib yurishni odat qilganlar, bu bilan ular bashang kiyinib yuruvchi ahli dunyolardan farqli hayot tarzini oʻzlarida namoyon etganlar, deydi.

Tasavvuf va "sufiy" soʻzlari IX asrning boshlarida yashagan Abu Hoshim Sufiydan boshlab joriy etilgan. Undan oldingi davrlarda bu atama oʻrnida "zuhd" ("zohidlik", "tarkidunyochilik"), "taqvodorlik", "parhezkorlik" kabi soʻzlar ishlatilgan. Ibn Xaldunning fikriga koʻra, sahobalar, tobeinlar va ulardan keyingi asr kishilarida hidoyat, ibodat, taqvo va zohidlik kabi his-tuygʻular mujassam boʻlgan. Lekin hijratning II asri va undan keyingi davrga kelib, odamlarning koʻpchiligida mazkur xususiyatlar oʻrnida dunyoparastlik, din ishlariga beparvolik, kibr va riyokorlik kabi salbiy xususiyatlar paydo boʻla boshlagandan keyin obidlik va zoqidlikni ixtiyor qilgan bir guruh kishilar Tasavvuf va sufiylik nomi bilan ajralib chiqqanlar.

Tasavvuf turlicha talqin qilingan. Masalan: Maʼruf alKarxiy (815 y.v.e.) fikricha, "tasavvuf — haqiqat sari intilish, odamlardan tamagirlik qilmaslik va faqirlikni ixtiyor etishdir". Zunnun al Misriy (859 y.v.e.), "Soʻfiy boylik istab oʻzini charchatmas va yoʻqotgan boyligiga achinib, bezovta boʻlmas", desa, Junayd al Bagʻdodiy (909 y.v.e.) "tasavvuf — qalbni sof tutmoq, tugʻma zaiflik va noxushaxloqlardan forigʻ boʻlib, hayvoniy va nafsoniy tuygʻular ustidan gʻalaba qilmoq", deb taʼrif bergan. Yana u "tasavvuf bir uy boʻlsa, shariat unga kiradigan eshikdir", degan. Soʻfi Olloyor bu taʼrifni quvvatlab: Shariatsiz kishi uchea havogʻa Koʻngil berma aningdek xudnamogʻa deb yozadi. Misirlik olim Ibrohim Basyuniy "Islomda Tasavvufning paydo boʻlishi" kitobida hijriy 3 va 4-asrlarda yashab oʻtgan olimlarning tasavvuf haqidagi 40 ta taʼrifini keltiradi.

Xulosa qilib aytilish mumkinki, tasavvuf islom shariati talablarini ham ixlos bilan bajargan xolda zuhd, taqvo, kamtarlik kabi olijanob fazilatlarini oʻzida mujassam etib, nafsni poklash yoʻli bilan komil inson darajasiga erishishga harakat qilishdan iborat. Tasavvuf tasavvufning oʻziga xos istilohi mavjud. Masalan, tasavvuf ilmidan saboq beruvchi shaxs — shayx, murshid, pir, eshon, xoja, mavlo, mavlono, maxdum kabi unvonlar bilan tanilgan. Tasavvufdan saboq oluvchi shaxs — murid, solik, ahli dil, ahli hol, mutasavvif kabi nomlar bilan atalgan. Tasavvuf boʻyicha oliy maqomlarga erishgan sohibkaromat pirlar — valiy, avliyo, qutb, aqtob, avtod, chilton, abdol, abror, ahror, nujabo, nuqabo, siddiq, gʻavs va h.k. deyilgan. Tasavvuf ahli baʼzan oshiq, faqir, haqir, darvesh, qalandar, zohid, orif, devona, ahli muhabbat, ahli suluk, rijolulgʻayb, savdoyi, gado kabi atamalar bilan ham ifoda etilgan.

Tasavvuf istilohi asosida ijod etgan shoirlar majoz uslubini tanlaganlar. Shuning uchun haqiqat, majoz, tashbeh, istiora kabi mantiqiy qoidalardan boxabar boʻlmagan kitobxon Navoiy, Fuzuliy, Atoyi, Umar Xayyom kabi mumtoz adabiyot namoyandalarning sheʼrlarini toʻla anglashi qiyin kechadi. Tasavvuf tarixida koʻpgina olimlar tasavvufga doir soʻzlar izohiga bagʻishlangan lugʻat va qomuslarni yozib qodirganlar. Ulardan ayrimlari Oʻzbekiston Fanlar Akademiyasi Sharqshunoslik instituti qoʻlyozmalar fondida saqlanmoqda.

Tasavvuf tariqatlarining insoniyat ma'naviyatini yuksaltirishga qo'shib kelayotgan benazir hissasi butun dunyo xalqi tomonidan e'tirof etilsada, ba'zan islom olamida tasavvufga salbiy nazar bilan qarash, uning tariqatlari, mashoyixlar va karomatlarini inkor etish ko'zga tashlanadi. Burhoniddin al Biqoiy (1406— 1480)ning "Tasavvuf inqirozi", Abdurahmon Dimashqiyaning "Naqshbandiya tahlili" kitobi va boshqa kitoblarda tasavvufning barcha tariqatlari va ularga doir asarlar hamda mashoyixlar qattiq tanqid qilingan. Aziz avliyolarning maqbara va mozorlarini ziyorat qilish shirk deb sanalgan. Vaholanki, ularning bu da'volari shar'an asossizdir.

Islom huquqshunosligida, ya'ni shar'iy ko'rsatmalarni amalga tadbiiq etishda 4 ta fiqxiy mazhab bo'lganidek, Tasavvufda ham bir necha tariqatlar shakllangan. Mashhurlari — tayfuriya, junaydiya, hakimiya, qodiriya, yassaviylik, malomatiylar, rifoia, kubroviylik, suhravardiylik, chishtiya, akbariya, shoziliya, bektoshiya, mavlaviya, naqshbandiya, sanusiya tariqatlaridir. Mustaqillik yillari mamlakatimizda tasavvuf tariqatlarini o'rganish, unga doir asarlarni tarjima qilish, atoqli mashoyixlarning maqbaralarini qayta qurish va ta'mirlashga ahamiyat berilmoqda. Hakim Termiziy, Najmiddin Kubro, Abduxoliq G'ijduvoni, Xoja Ahmad Yassaviy, Bahouddin Naqshband, Xoja Ahror Valiy, Shayx Zayniddin, Zangi ota, Shayx Xovandi Tohur va boshqa ko'plab tasavvuf tariqatlariga mansub piri komillarning hayot va ijodlarini chuqur o'rganish, qoldirgan asarlaridan xalqimizni bahramand etish borasida muayyan ishlar qilindi .

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